

Brune stress drop, fault slip distribution and high frequency radiation during the 2016-2018 Amatrice-Visso-Norcia seismic sequence

1: Summary and Motivation

How well can we measure Brune Stress Drops?
Do they vary with magnitude? Or time? Or location?
What does Brune stress drop tell us? High stress drop? Source complexity?
High ground acceleration?

2016-2018 Amatrice-Visso-Norcia Earthquake sequence

The predominantly normal-faulting sequence of earthquakes in the Apennines of central Italy included nine Mw > 5 earthquakes.

Multiple researchers have estimated Brune-style stress drops for earthquakes in this sequence, using different methods, providing an opportunity to compare systematic and random variability.

Finite fault inversions published for the three largest earthquakes: 24 August (Amatrice, Mw 6), 26 August (Visso, Mw 5.9) and 30 October (Norcia, Mw 6.5) allow us to compare the estimates of Brune stress drop with the slip distribution (and its predicted stress release), for the similar-sized Amatrice and Visso earthquakes.

We use this well-recorded earthquake sequence to address the outstanding questions above.

(See Poster 195: Introduction to the SCEC Community Stress Drop Validation Study TAG)

2: Spectral Modeling for Brune Stress drop

This Study: Spectral Fitting and Spectral Ratios:

We use two different approaches to calculate the source spectra, corner frequency, and Brune stress drop of 30 of the larger events (Calderoni & Abercrombie, 2020). We use moments of these 30 target events independently calculated using regional MT inversions.

1: SP We calculate k by averaging 14 regional earthquakes (equation 1). Then correct the spectra using this attenuation model and fit the result using the Brune model (equation 2).
2: SR: We select an empirical Green's function (EGF) earthquake for each target earthquake, and the model spectral ratio between target and EGF events using the Brune Model

We compare our results to those of Bindi *et al* (2020) who used a generalized inversion (spectral decomposition) method to estimate moment, corner frequency and regional attenuation for over 4000 events.

Attenuation Model:

$$A(f) = A_0 e^{-\pi f \kappa} \quad 1$$

Brune Model:

$$A(f) = \frac{M_0}{\left(1 + \frac{f}{f_c}\right)^2} \quad 2$$

For each earthquake, we show:

Our attenuation-corrected Displacement spectra and best fits (SP)

Spectral Ratios with different EGF events – only ones with sufficient low-frequency energy are used

Azimuthal variation of the corner frequency (f_c) and stress drop measurements

Comparison of our fits, and those of Bindi *et al.* (2020) to example spectral ratios. We also included the best fitting model in which stress drop of target and EGF events are identical.

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Location Map, and cross sections of main fault plane

3: Comparison of Brune Spectral Model Results from Different Studies

We compare our results for Brune-style stress drop with those from Bindi *et al.* (2020). The inter-study variation is significantly larger than the standard errors produced by any single study, and the (apparent?) magnitude dependence varies. All approaches find that the M6 Amatrice earthquake had a higher stress drop than the similar-sized M5.9 Visso earthquake.

I am still working on this figure!! I want to add error bars and make colours match your spectral ratio fits

Comparison of Estimated Corner Frequencies and Seismic Moments

4: Comparison of Spectral and Finite-Fault Modeling: Amatrice M6 & Visso M5.9

Finite Fault Inversion:

The finite fault inversions of the similar sized Amatrice and Visso earthquakes (Chiaraluce *et al.*, 2017) found that the Visso earthquake had the larger region of concentrated, higher slip, whereas the Amatrice earthquake had multiple, lower slip, sub-events.

The spectra of the moment-rate functions are consistent with the spectral analyses; the spectrum of the Amatrice earthquake contains more high frequency energy than that of the Visso earthquake.

This comparison of two similar-sized earthquakes suggests that consistent measurement of a higher corner frequency and Brune stress drop indicates greater high-frequency ground motion, but may correspond to greater rupture complexity rather than higher stress drop (and higher slip).

Source time functions and Spectra from Finite Fault Inversions

Amatrice has more high frequency energy and higher corner frequency than Visso
M0 Amatrice ~ 1.4 x M0 Visso

Higher Brune (spectral) stress drop = higher high frequency ground motion, BUT lower and smaller region of peak slip with higher complexity of slip

Comparison of Finite Fault Distributions from Chiaraluce *et al.* (2017) and Tinti *et al.* (2016), and their estimated stress release, with the Spectral estimates from Bindi *et al.* (2020) and this study.

5: Conclusions

- Absolute values of Brune Stress Drop depend strongly on path corrections, and are usually outside the uncertainties of other methods.
- Relative values of Brune Stress Drop are better, and correlate across studies.
- Comparison with Finite Fault Models reveals a high Brune stress drop represents stronger high-frequency ground motion BUT may indicate more complex slip-distribution rather than concentrated high slip and stress release.
- Brune-style spectral stress drop may be more reliable for ground motion prediction than for analysis of earthquake rupture physics.

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